

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING OF GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES WITH INORGANIC PHOSPHATE CEMENT MATRIX: COMPARISON OF INBUILT ABAQUS CONCRETE MODELS

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1. Introduction

Cement composites are promising materials particularly for the construction industry as they overcome crucial drawbacks of more commonly used polymer matrix composite materials. Contrarily to traditional organic resins (epoxy), the Inorganic Phosphate Cement (IPC), developed at Vrije Universiteit Brussel [1], is incombustible. The IPC matrix moreover has a neutral pH after hardening, consequently it is not chemically aggressive for E-glass fibres, which are cheap in production [2]. Finally, the fine grained IPC can impregnate very dense chopped strand mats which results in fibre volume fractions of more than 20% [3] which is much larger than 5% that is commonly achieved with textile reinforced concrete.

Currently, few research is performed on the constitutive modelling of these cement composites particularly within commercially available Finite Element Method (FEM) software [4][5]. The subject of this paper is therefore to study the aptness of the material models available in the FEM software Abaqus to model the mechanical behaviour of strain hardening cement composites consisting of an E-Glass Fibre chopped strand mat Reinforcement and an Inorganic Phosphate Cement matrix (GFR-IPC).

The main difficulties with the modelling of the GFR-IPC are caused by discrepancy between tensile and compressive mechanical properties; and the nonlinearity of the tensile behaviour after cracking of the matrix (see Fig. 1). Therefore this paper focuses on the inbuilt models for concrete offered by

the software Abaqus. Models taken into consideration are Concrete Damaged Plasticity and Concrete Smeared Cracking. Both models have a high potential of modelling the cement composite when assuming homogeneity of the material on 10 mm scale [6], which is valid due to the high fibre volume fraction (> 20%), and the homogeneous distribution and random orientation of the fibres using chopped strand mats [5].

This paper compares the two concrete models for their adequacy in modelling the cement composite material. After a brief theoretical background on the models, this paper discusses the used material parameters implemented in both models. Both numerical models were based on the uniaxial tensile laboratory tests performed on GFR-IPC with a fibre volume fraction of 23%. Models were verified by biaxial tension-tension tests on both a square plate and a cruciform specimen [5]. Comparison of numerical and experimental results yields conclusions on the validity of both concrete models for the modelling of strain-hardening cement composites.

2. Theoretical background on the FEM models

2.1. Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP)

The Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) model in Abaqus [7] is based on the yield surface proposed by Lubliner et al. [8] with the modifications suggested by Lee and Fenves [9]. The yield surface is a modified Drucker-Prager function. The evolution of

the surface is controlled by two sets of strain hardening variables, $\tilde{\varepsilon}_t^{pl}$ and $\tilde{\varepsilon}_c^{pl}$, inputted by the user, corresponding to tensile-cracking and compressive-crushing failure respectively. Additionally, the deviatoric cross-section can be modified by the K_c factor which can be described by the yield condition ratio along tensile and compressive meridians. The value of the K_c factor can vary from 1.0 to 0.5; while 1.0 corresponds to a circular cross-section as in the Drucker-Prager model [10] (see Fig. 2). Finally, the yield surface is modified by the ratio of the initial biaxial to uniaxial compressive strength f_{b0}/f_{c0} .

The hyperbolic function of the non-associated flow potential G is given by the following formula:

$$G = \sqrt{(\varepsilon\sigma_{t0} \tan \psi)^2 + \bar{q}^2} - \bar{p} \tan \psi \quad (1)$$

, where σ_{t0} is the uniaxial tensile strength, ψ is the dilatation angle and ε is the plastic potential eccentricity. Figure 3 explains the physical meaning of all these parameters.

The model expresses damage of the material by the scalar damage factor, which decreases the stiffness during unloading. Figure 4 illustrates the idea of degradation of the material for a uniaxial stress-strain relation. As Figure 4 shows, the damage evolution for concrete in tension is characterised by strain softening (descending stress-strain branch). One important question of the present research is to find arguments to show whether this model can also be applied to strain-hardening cement composites such as GFR-IPC.

The numerical formulation of the damage is as follows. For the uniaxial case, the stresses can be derived by the plastic strains:

$$\sigma_t = \sigma_t(\tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p, \tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p) \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_c(\tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p, \tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p) \quad (3)$$

The indexes 't' and 'c' correspond to tension and compression respectively. In case of uniaxial loading, the equivalent plastic strain rate can be written as follows:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_t^p = \dot{\varepsilon}_{11}^p \text{ and } \dot{\varepsilon}_c^p = -\dot{\varepsilon}_{11}^p$$

In order to calculate the Cauchy stress (σ) and the effective stress ($\bar{\sigma}$) the following formulas are used, assuming that E_0 is the initial stiffness of the material (undamaged):

$$\sigma_t = (1 - d_t)E_0(\varepsilon_t - \tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p) \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_c = (1 - d_c)E_0(\varepsilon_c - \tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p) \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_t = \frac{\sigma_t}{(1-d_t)} = E_0(\varepsilon_t - \tilde{\varepsilon}_t^p) \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_c = \frac{\sigma_c}{(1-d_c)} = E_0(\varepsilon_c - \tilde{\varepsilon}_c^p) \quad (7)$$

Factors d_t and d_c can vary from 0 (undamaged stated) to 1 (total damage of material).

The equation of the damage evolution factors can be generalized to the complex stress state. The equivalent strain rate is then evaluated by the formula:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_t^p = r(\hat{\sigma})\hat{\varepsilon}_{\max}^p \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_c^p = (r(\hat{\sigma}) - 1)\hat{\varepsilon}_{\min}^p \quad (9)$$

Where $\hat{\varepsilon}_{\max}^p$ and $\hat{\varepsilon}_{\min}^p$ are maximum and minimum eigen values of tensor $\hat{\varepsilon}^p$. The symbol $r(\hat{\sigma})$ depends on the principal stresses and equals

$$r(\hat{\sigma}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 \langle \hat{\sigma}_i \rangle}{\sum_{i=1}^3 |\hat{\sigma}_i|} \quad (10)$$

, where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is the Macauley bracket

$$\langle x \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (x + |x|) \quad (11)$$

2.2. Concrete Smeared Cracking (CSC)

Just like the CPD model, the Concrete Smeared Cracking (SCS) model [7] does not track the crack pattern but simulates 'cracked' behaviour as the effect it has on the stiffness and stress state. After detection of 'the crack', the tension-compression anisotropy, caused by matrix cracking, is introduced into the constitutive behaviour by damaged elasticity. The direction of cracks is derived by the fixed orthogonal crack model, while their detection is determined by the simple Coulomb line failure surface [7].

The model is also based on the theory of plasticity with associated flow and isotropic hardening. The two different yield surfaces are postulated for compression and tension (see Fig. 5). Additionally,

the following four failure ratios must be specified to describe the yield surface:

- the ultimate biaxial to uniaxial compressive stress;
- the value of uniaxial tensile stress at failure (cracking) to the ultimate uniaxial compressive stress;
- the magnitude of the principal component of the plastic strain at ultimate stress in biaxial compression to that in uniaxial compression;
- the tensile principal stress at cracking - in plane stress, when the other principal stress is equal to ultimate compressive stress - to the tensile stress at cracking in uniaxial tension.

From the yield surface, the crack is detected together with its orientation. Consequently, ‘plastic’ strains related to such a crack are calculated. These strains, in a single integration point, are treated as elastic strain in the crack direction and as plastic strains in others. After crack detection, the damaged elasticity describes the post-failure behaviour of the concrete. Damaged elasticity is described in the following manner:

- assuming α as crack direction, the following direct stress $\sigma_{\alpha\alpha}$ and direct strain $\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{el}$ ¹ correspond,
- then \mathbf{D} which is the elastic stiffness matrix, does not change in $D_{\alpha\alpha\beta\gamma}$ if $\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha} \leq 0$,
- if $0 < \varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha} < \varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{open}$, $D_{\alpha\alpha\alpha\alpha} = \frac{\sigma_{\alpha\alpha}^{open}}{\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{open}}$
- if $\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha} = \varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{open}$, $D_{\alpha\alpha\alpha\alpha} = \frac{d\sigma_{\alpha\alpha}^{open}}{d\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{open}}$,

where $\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{open} = \max(\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{el})$ and $\sigma_{\alpha\alpha}^{open}$ corresponds to $\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{open}$ (tension stiffening input data)

3. Material modelling

3.1. Material description

The cement composite modelled in this paper is made of IPC and E-glass fibre mats. The inorganic phosphate cement matrix was developed at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel. It is a two-component system, consisting of a calcium silicate powder and a phosphate acid based solution of metaloxides [6]. Like other cementitious materials, unreinforced IPC

is brittle. The compressive strength is about 80 MPa, while the tensile strength is ten times smaller and varies from 6 to 8 MPa [6]. The stiffness of IPC is less than normal concrete and is equal to 18 GPa. The fibreglass used in the research is chopped glass fibre mats with a density of 300 g/m². The diameter of each fibre is 14 μm , the length is about 50 mm and the number of fibres per bundle is approximately 540.

The mechanical behaviour of the composite is significantly different in tension and compression due to the brittleness of the matrix. In compression, it can be assumed to be linear until failure[6]. Contrarily, the tensile behaviour is nonlinear. At low tensile stresses, the composite is stiff as both components (fibres and matrix) contribute to the bearing of the applied tensile load. At the value of about 7 MPa the matrix cracks and the behaviour of the composite relies only on the glass fibre reinforcement, leading to a much lower post-cracking stiffness than before crack initiation (see Fig. 1).

3.2. Identification of the model parameters

3.2.1. Parameters common for both concrete models

Both models assume in-plane isotropy. This may be motivated by the random orientation of the filaments and high volume fraction ($> 20\%$), as well as homogeneous distribution of the fibres that is assured by the use of fibre mats. Furthermore, both models were based on the uniaxial test data (see Fig. 1). After the strain-hardening modelling, an artificial steep softening branch has been added to simulate failure of the material (see Fig. 7). It decreases the uniaxial tensile stress from about 61 MPa at 1.27 % strain to 1 MPa at 3% strain, Figure 7 shows the input tension and compression data taken for the simulation.

3.2.2. Concrete Damaged Plasticity

Besides the uniaxial data, additional parameters must be implemented to describe the multi-axial behaviour of the composite. These parameters were determined either from the analysis of the biaxial tests by one of the authors – Tysmans [5] or in agreement with the default values for concrete. The model assumes the following data:

¹ Bar over repeated indexes implies no summation

- the *dilatation angle* was assumed as for normal concrete 36° ;
- the potential flow *eccentricity* was assumed as default 0.1;
- the proportion of the ultimate compressive stress in a biaxial test to the ultimate uniaxial compressive stress (f_{b0}/f_{c0}) was taken as 1.0 according to conclusions drawn by Tysmans [5];
- the K_c coefficient determining the shape of the deviatoric cross-section in the flow surface was taken as 0.667;
- the *viscosity parameter* was taken at a relatively low value of 0.001 to improve the rate of convergence.

3.2.3. Concrete Smeared Cracking

Similarly to CDP model, to fulfil CSC model, the following parameter must be implemented. These parameters are failure ratios and they were assumed as follows:

- the ultimate biaxial to uniaxial compressive stress was, analogically to the CDP model, taken as 1.0;
- the value of uniaxial tensile stress at failure (i.e. crack initiation at 7.2 MPa) to the ultimate uniaxial compressive stress (at value of 80 MPa) equaled 0.09;
- the magnitude of the principal component of the plastic strain at ultimate stress in biaxial compression to the uniaxial compression, was taken as 1.0 as it will not influence the tension-tension test simulation;
- the tensile principal stress at cracking - in plane stress, when the other principal stress is equal to ultimate compressive stress- to the tensile stress in the uniaxial tension, was taken as 1.0 because of the assumption of biaxial independence.

4. Biaxial experiment set-up

This paragraph briefly discusses the experimental program performed to obtain the biaxial strain data for the evaluation of both models. The tests were performed by Tysmans at the department of

Mechanics of Materials and Constructions (MEMC) of Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) [5]. The experimental program subjected a cruciform specimen to in-plane biaxial loading with two different load ratios:

- with an equal load applied in both directions,
- with the load in the one direction twice bigger than in the perpendicular direction.

The test set-up (see Fig. 6) was built up specially for biaxial testing at MEMC. It consists of Instron horizontal biaxial test bench and two sets of 50 mm long clamps. The instrumentation of the test was performed by the full-field measuring technique of digital image correlation (DIC). DIC measures a random speckle pattern on the surface. A random speckle pattern is applied onto the surface on the specimen. Correlation of pictures taken from speckled surface at subsequent load steps with a reference (unloaded) image yields the displacement, and thus strains, of the surface. As the full field measurement technique allows the computation of the entire strain field of the specimen surface instead of the discrete strains that are measured with strain gauges, a more in-depth comparison with the FE model is facilitated (see par. 5.3).

5. Numerical model

The appropriateness of both concrete models for the modelling of strain-hardening cement composites is evaluated by the simulation of two biaxial tensile tests: (i) a numerical biaxial tensile test on a simple plate geometry that allows analytical interpretation, and (ii) an experimental biaxial tensile test on a complex cruciform specimen that allows numerical-experimental comparison.

5.1. Boundary conditions and mesh description

For saving computational time in the numerical test, only one quarter of the cruciform specimen was modelled with symmetry boundary conditions. Both models use S4R – 4 node quadrilateral shell elements with reduced Gauss points of integration. The convergence of the results was checked on three different meshes with an average element size of 14, 7 and 3.5 mm respectively.

5.2. Load cases

The biaxial load application on the simple plate specimen on the one hand, and on the cruciform specimen on the other hand, were as follows. The square specimen with a side of 280 mm and thickness of 2 mm was loaded in tension by displacing the edge (over its whole length) up to the value of 2 mm. In order to model the biaxial tension laboratory test on the cruciform specimen, two simulations were performed for each material model, in correspondence with the two different load cases that were applied during the tests:

- equibiaxial tension (1-1);
- tensile load two times higher in one direction than in the perpendicular one (2-1).

In both cases, the load was applied by forcing a displacement of the specimen edges at the position of the clamps, over the edge length of 25 mm (half of the clamp length because of symmetry modelling). In the case of equibiaxial tests the displacement was equal to 1/400 of the specimen length, 0.7 mm. In the second, (2-1) load case, displacements were 0.7 mm and 0.175 mm respectively.

6. Results and discussion

The comparison of the models was done on four different levels:

- stress-strain response of the simple square plate;
- force-strain response in the centre of the cruciform specimen;
- distribution of the principal strains over the entire surface of the cruciform specimen;
- failure simulation.

The presented results correspond to the finest mesh (average element size of 3.5 mm).

6.1. Stress-strain response of plate specimen

Purely numerical - uniaxial and equibiaxial - tensile tests on a square specimen were performed to verify the stress-strain response in both models. Figure 8 shows the comparison of the stress-strain relation of the uniaxial and equibiaxial tests, with the input data based on the laboratory uniaxial tensile test (as discussed in paragraph 4).

Both models agree in simulation of the uniaxial behaviour, proving correct identification of the

model parameters. Biaxial behaviour indicates only slightly less stiff behaviour in the Concrete Damaged Plasticity model, in contrast to the Concrete Smeared Cracking model (the ultimate stress is around 47 MPa, which is approximately 22 % less than the initial uniaxial 60 MPa for the same ultimate strain. This implies that the biaxial behaviour simulated with CSC will underestimate the stiffness and the ultimate force, while simultaneously overestimating the strain level.

6.2. Force-strain response of cruciform specimen

As from the experiments only the strain can be measured, the comparison between numerical and experimental behaviour of the cruciform specimen will be discussed based on the force-strain diagram. The centre of the specimen was taken as a discrete point from which the principal strain data was read. The applied force was taken as the reaction force at the position of the clamps and then multiplied by 2 due to symmetry. Respectively for load case 1 and 2, Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 show the force-strain diagram of both material models compared with the results of the laboratory test. In the first load case, equibiaxial tension (Fig. 9), the results from the CDP analysis correspond well with the experimental data. In contrast, the CSC model indicates a much larger decrease in stiffness after cracking than experimentally observed. In the second load case (2-1), both models agree up to a point of the load of around 6500 N, after which the CSC analysis crashes (see Fig. 10).

6.3. Strain distribution

Thanks to the use of the DIC full-field method for measuring the strains during the experiment, the numerical models can be compared to the laboratory experiments globally. The principal strain contour diagram is compared to the experimental results at the value of 8 kN. Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 present the results from both load cases (1-1 and 2-1 respectively).

The distribution of the strains in both models corresponds well with the experimental data. The strain concentration occurring close to the rounded cut is predicted by the models; however the value is

slightly overestimated – 1.05% in CDP model and 1.1%, while in the experiment it did not exceed 1%.

6.4. Ultimate tensile force of cruciform specimen

In the CDP model the ultimate tensile force is taken as the maximal value of the force during the simulation, while in the CSC it is the value of the force when the analysis crashes. Table 1 compares the results of the simulations with the experimental data for both load cases.

The CDP model gives a reasonable approximation of the values of the ultimate tensile force, while the CSC model is not always reliable. In the case of equibiaxial loading (1-1), the CDP model predicts an ultimate tensile force of 9.8 kN, whereas the CSC model estimates a value of 8.2 kN. Both material models give a difference between numerical test and average laboratory test results of the same order of magnitude (10.1% and 7.8% for the CDP model and the CSC model respectively). In contrast, for the (2-1) load case, the difference between both models is significant. The CDP model differs 3.4% from the experimental average while the CSC model gives a much larger error of 33.8%.

Contrarily to the CSC model, the CDP model can simulate the strain softening branch on the equilibrium path. In this manner the failure can be simulated.

7. Conclusions

The numerical simulation of strain-hardening cement composite materials, such as IPC with E-glass fibre reinforcing strand mats, was performed by means of two concrete models available in the Abaqus material library. Both models are based on the theory of plasticity with the assumption of in-plane isotropy.

From the comparison of the biaxial tension-tension experiments with the numerical simulations, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- both models are capable of simulating the uniaxial strain hardening behaviour in tension;
- the parameters for both models were well identified, which is proven by the close prediction of the strain distribution across the whole area of the analysed specimen;

- for the numerical simulation of equibiaxial tension in a square plate, the CDP model corresponds well to theoretical predictions, while the CSC model decreases the ultimate stress of around 22%;
- the CDP model is able to simulate failure of the material by implementing a descending strain-softening branch, while CSC crashes disabling to finish simulation;
- the ultimate tensile force can be practically predicted by the CDP model.

In conclusion, the CDP model proves to be better in predicting the ultimate force as well as the equilibrium path; nevertheless, the CSC model requires less parameters, which are moreover easier to define.

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Fig. 1. Nonlinear uniaxial tensile behaviour of GFR-IPC with a fibre volume fraction of 23% [5]

Fig. 2 Yield surface in deviatoric plane, corresponding to different values of K_c – value 1.0 corresponds to the classic Drucker-Prager yield surface, while 0.667 corresponds to concrete behaviour in triaxial compression [7]

Fig. 4 Uniaxial stress-strain curves for normal concrete illustrating the damage idea: (a) for tension, (b) for compression [7]

Fig. 3 The hyperbolic flow potentials in the meridian plane with physical interpretation of the input parameters [7]

Fig. 5 Failure surface for Concrete Smeared Cracking in tension and compression [7]

Fig. 6 Biaxial experiment set-up [5]

Fig. 7 Tension and compression data input for the simulation, with additional artificial descending strain-softening branches

Fig. 8 Comparison of stress-strain relation in both models in the tests performed on the square specimen

Fig. 9. Diagram of force to first principal strain in the centre of specimen, comparing laboratory and numerical results, load case 1-1

Fig. 10. Diagram of force to first principal strain in the centre of specimen, comparing laboratory and numerical results, load case 2-1

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Fig. 11 Comparison of principal strain distribution in laboratory test and numerical simulation, in the equibiaxial load case (1-1) (top experiment, bottom-left CDP, bottom right CSC)

Fig. 12 Comparison of principal strain distribution in laboratory test and numerical simulation, in the load case (2-1) (top experiment, bottom-left CDP, bottom right CSC)

Table 1 Comparison of ultimate applied load [kN]

Test\experiment	specimen 1	specimen 2	specimen 3	CDP	CSC
Test (1-1)	8.9	8.4	9.4	9.8	8.2
Test (2-1)	10.2	8.6	10.2	10	6.4

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